

Deliverable 4.1

REPORT ON DATA REQUIREMENTS AND AVAILABLE DATA MAPPING

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1. List of abbreviations and definitions

Table 1.1 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name
Achilles	Automated Characterization of Health Information at Large-Scale Longitudinal Evidence Systems
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (classification system)
CDM	Common Data Model
DARWIN EU [®]	Data Analysis and Real World Interrogation Network
DMP	Data Management Plan
DQD	Data Quality Dashboard

DoA	Deed of Agreement
ECMO	Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation
EHDEN	European Health Data Evidence Network
EMA	European Medicine's Agency
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
EU	European Union
FDA	U.S. Food and Drug Administration
FVIII	Factor VIII (factor eight)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GOSH	Great Ormond Street Hospital
HADES	Health Analytics Data-to-Evidence Suite

HSJD	Hospital Sant Joan de Déu
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PESERS	Pediatric Sepsis Early Recognition Score
PHEMS	Pediatric Hospitals as European drivers for multi-party computation and synthetic data generation capabilities across clinical specialties and data types
PICU	Pediatric Intensive Care Unit
UC	Use Case
WP	Work package

2. Introduction

2.1. Why OMOP

The PHEMS consortium has chosen the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) to store and conduct research for the three use cases and as the basis to create anonymous synthetic data.

The OMOP CDM provides a standardized framework for the organization and representation of observational healthcare data (1). Hereby the adoption of this model empowers researchers by enabling data sharing, collaborations, and comparisons of studies through increased interoperability of data. Moreover, the model has been designed with scalability in mind, accommodating large-scale datasets from various sources such as EHRs, insurance claims databases, and clinical registries. Its flexible structure can handle a wide range of clinical concepts.

The above utilities have been demonstrated within large-scale federated analysis networks, where the OMOP CDM has been used as the data model for large, impactful projects, such as the IMI EHDEN consortium, the EMA's DARWIN EU project and the FDA's Sentinel Initiative (2-4).

Overall, this makes the OMOP CDM a highly suitable model to be adopted in the PHEMS project, which aims to address EU GDPR data sharing challenges by developing a decentralized health data ecosystem to enable federated analytics.

The guideline aims to ensure that the OMOP data quality of all hospitals aligns with EHDEN/OMOP standards.

2.2. How to use this document

The current document describes the procedure for mapping the variables of interest for each PHEMS WP4 use case. One of the clinical partners has already mapped a portion of their source data to OMOP, including some of the variables of interest for PHEMS. For this partner, the current document provides information about already done mappings and an OMOP mapping roadmap for

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mappings still missing to enable clinical use cases. For the clinical partners that have not mapped source data of interest to OMOP yet, this document proposes OMOP codes and describes the procedure for mapping the variables of interest for each PHEMS WP4 use case.

The variables of interest for each UC, together with the OMOP codes used at each hospital as were collected and used for this document can be found in the [data dictionary final variable list 04-Mar-2024 locked.xlsx](#) (5).

Additionally at the end of the document an overview of the data quality assessment tools developed within OHDSI, EHDEN and DARWIN EU can be found. It is advised that after each ETL iteration these tools should be utilized and the results should be reviewed to ensure the OMOP tables are up to the latest standards.

The document is aimed at ETL developers and analysts. Although the OMOP CDM will not be described below, in the next section the reader can find a list of available resources to better understand the model and the open source analytics. In addition, at the end of the document there are introductions to some of the tooling the OHDSI community, the Darwin EU and EHDEN EU projects have developed. Furthermore, a mapping of all the variables of interest to standard OMOP concepts has been provided as a guideline.

The workflow to convert data to the OMOP CDM starts from the source data. During the ETL preparation stage one makes the semantic and syntactic decisions for the task. In the WP4 case, since the source data is not shared within the consortium, the semantic part of the preparation was performed based on the UC variables of interest (5). This must be considered when using the guidelines below, as the source terms might differ from the variables of interest.

The four sites providing information at this stage of the project were also asked to provide any available OMOP mappings they have done, together with a WhiteRabbit scan report of the data (6). Only partial information has been provided to the Hyve team at the time of writing v1.0.0 of the “Report on data requirements and available data mapping”, i.e. only one site provided codes associated with the variables of interest according to the Use Cases and a different site provided a WhiteRabbit scan report but without a data dictionary. When the information is received, if it differs from the proposed OMOP mapping one can find explanations for the diversion. Then, the ETL engineers have to make a decision in collaboration with a medical expert and the Hyve team on the best way to handle it. The options are either using the variable mapping for the source term as suggested by the sites, or using the exact concept mapping and including a list of codes when conducting the analysis. More on concept sets can be found in section 6.4.1 of this document as well as the ATLAS available information in the OHDSI resources.

Finally, the sections below have been split into variables shared between the UCs and individual UC sections. This approach was chosen to avoid repeated information and make the document more readable and searchable.

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3. Resources

As mentioned above the current document will not include explicit explanations on the OMOP CDM. However, there is a plethora of open-source material to read or watch through to learn everything about the model.

The best place to start your journey is the EHDEN academy platform (7). Anyone can create an account there and browse videos from the basics of the OMOP CDM to more specific material on data quality and analytics. Given the versatile background of the consortium we would advise everyone to watch the introductory videos to OHDSI first. For the engineers, there is material on the ETL preparation tools, White Rabbit, Rabbit in a Hat and Usagi, as well as the Data Quality Dashboard (DQD) (6,8-10). Moreover, analysts can find information on how to use ATLAS and the HADES packages (11,12).

Another great reference page is the OMOP CDM GitHub page (13). This serves as full documentation on the CDM, explaining all the tables and fields, addressing current conventions, and includes an introduction to the work of the OMOP CDM working group. No matter the level of experience, this is a great page to refer to during every step of your OMOP journey.

Lastly, the OHDSI forums are the place to ask questions and raise concerns over any issue related to the model, its utility or the tools (14). Here you can also find collaborators.

4. Understanding the source

The process of mapping observational health data to the OMOP format can be long and arduous. For it to go as smoothly as possible, substantive knowledge of the target data model, as well as the source data is required. Because of this, developers of the ETL should also approach the standardization process with the highest possible level of understanding of the source data. Often, this is gained through extensive collaboration and discussions with the relevant stakeholders responsible for acquiring, processing, or handling the source data.

For this deliverable [4.1] to be done in a comprehensible, and efficient way, a data source questionnaire was disseminated across the different hospital data sites to be answered by the relevant clinical and technical partners. This was done to gain the best

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perspective of the data being mapped from each site and the requirements specific to an individual hospital. In doing so, each hospital site was also able to check that all variables of interest were included for the respective use case. The questionnaire was not used to inform this document but the Data Management Plan (DMP) [deliverable 4.2] (15).

5. Variable list

5.1. Common variables across use cases

5.1.1. General

The three WP4 use cases designed and curated a list of variables through regular meetings that would be essential for performing the analysis to answer the respective research questions. This main section of the document is based on the agreed variable list and makes suggestions on the OMOP CDM vocabulary mappings (5). The three use cases, although answering very different clinical questions, share some of the variables.

All reference tables follow a similar format with list of terms, presented in Table 5.1:

Table 5.1 Terms

Term	Refers to
PHEMS variable of interest	The variable as discussed in WP4 UC biweekly meetings. Can be found in the “data dictionary final variable list 04-Mar-2024 locked.xlsx” (5)
Suggested by	Indicates the WP4 collaborator that suggested the OMOP mapping. Only applicable in the Site information sections of the document. The rest of the tables are implicitly suggested by the Hyve.

Site using the unit/meas value	Indicates the WP4 collaborator that is using each unit. Only applicable to some of the table mappings; those units were provided by the sites.
OMOP CDM conceptId	The number (id) the target variable is represented by in the OMOP CDM vocabularies.
OMOP CDM concept name	The name of the target variable as it is represented in the OMOP CDM vocabularies.
OMOP CDM domain	The domain the target variable belongs to in the OMOP CDM vocabularies. This domain informs the OMOP CDM table for the variable to be stored at.

The overlap between the variables in the three use cases:

Figure 5.1 The number of variables per use case and the amount of overlapping

5.1.2. Demographics

All three use cases make use of demographic data obtained from their respective patient populations. In the OMOP CDM these records are mapped to the Person table, which functions as a central identity management table for all patients in the database. The Person table together with the Observation Period table are the only two required model tables.

In the OMOP CDM, each person is assigned an id, most of the time an autoincremented integer as a unique and persistent identifier to facilitate tracking of the patient's records across the various other CDM tables. There are some mandatory fields to map in the Person table and others highly recommended.

A patients' year of birth needs to be filled, while the birth month and day are recommended to map if the source data has provided the necessary level of detail.

Then the gender_concept_id should be filled to capture the biological sex of the patient at birth. Currently in the vocabularies, the only acceptable concepts are those of Male and Female.

The race_concept_id field aims to record the racial or ethnic background of a person. While this target field is mandatory, it should only be used when this information is explicitly recorded. If a patient's race or ethnicity cannot be established, then the concept should be mapped to 0. The acceptable concepts to be mapped here can be found on the Athena website by filtering the terms by domain: Race and concept: standard (16). A link to the terms can be found [here](#).

Lastly the Ethnicity field captures ethnicity as defined by the government of the United States. This field is also mandatory, but it should only be used if the source data is US-based. In the context of PHEMS, all patients should be mapped to 0 for this field.

Table 5.2 Patient demographics

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM	
	Table	Field
Date of birth	Person	year_of_birth month_of_birth day_of_birth birth_datetime
Date of death	Death	death_date

Age	Derived from the date of birth	
Sex	Person	gender_concept_id; Male [concept_id: 8507] and Female [concept_id: 8532]
Mortality	Derived from death table	

5.1.3. Start- and end dates

Start- and stop dates and times should be mapped as accurately as possible. All OMOP CDM tables require an associated date. In the case of measurements that occur only once, it is appropriate if only a start date(time) is mapped, pertaining as accurately as possible to the exact point at which the measurement commenced. A stop datetime should be mapped whenever it is available.

For continuous measurements, it is recommended to break these down into meaningful time sections (e.g. every 15') with an average measurement over this section; each section is then to be treated as its own measurement. As each of these timeframes will have its own record, it is consequently recommended to not make these frames any smaller than is necessary for meaningful analyses, as this could lead to an overshot of records which require significantly more computational power and time.

For discontinuous measurements, it is recommended to map at least the start datetime as accurately as possible and the stop datetime if available; if this is not available the stop date should be left blank or be the same as the start datetime.

5.1.4. Drug groups

Use cases 1 and 2 are interested in groups of drugs. The Hyve considered the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification System (ATC) and RxNorm vocabularies to represent these (17,18). In the OMOP CDM Vocabularies ATC is a classification system

and it is linked with the RxNorm/RxNorm Extension codes. The lists provided by the use cases are at ingredient level and this is how they have been represented below. However, if a data source contains more granular information on the drug, it is advised that the most granular information available is mapped to the OMOP CDM drug exposure table. This can then be considered when creating the groups for analysis. It is worth mentioning here that the [drug_era](#) table can also be used as it will group the continuous drug exposures into the ingredient level drug.

ATC is a standardized system for classifying drugs and medical substances. It uses unique codes to place drugs in a hierarchical order based on the organ system they affect as well as their therapeutic, pharmacological, or chemical properties. ATC codes can organize drugs systematically at five different levels and are widely used for drug classification and administration. ATC codes were initially considered as the vocabulary of choice for mapping the drug group variables for all use cases in PHEMS.

After efforts to find the appropriate ATC codes to represent the relevant source variables at the correct level of detail, it was evident that the drug list provided by UC1 and UC2 would not be represented well with ATC codes. Thus, the RxNorm vocabulary was chosen to represent the source data with OMOP concepts.

The RxNorm vocabulary is a well-known set of ontologies with several levels of classes representing the hierarchical system for classifying drugs on varying levels of granularity. Drugs are represented amongst various classes ranging from general Ingredients, down to the specific branded drug and box of the prescribed medicine. As a well-known standard, using RxNorm codes facilitates potential comparisons to prior studies from different countries. RxNorm provides a standard nomenclature for labeling clinical drugs concerning the active ingredient, strength, and dose administered to the patient. A limitation of the vocabulary is that it is US-centric and contains few non-US drugs. Fortunately, the RxNorm Extension vocabulary was curated by the OHDSI community to account for this. This drug domain incorporates international drug vocabularies into an RxNorm-like system. The suggested mappings below consider only the ingredients as no detailed information is available at this stage. However, if the route, strength, etc., of the drug is available at the source, follow the hierarchical tree and use the concept with the most granularity.

In order to recreate the drug groups, you can create concept sets. Creating concept sets shifts the focus of grouping the drugs, which are already stored in the OMOP CDM Drug exposure table, to the analysis stage. This holds the advantage as all drugs have been mapped as close to the source as possible and can all be represented and manually curated when choosing the group of interest.

The tables below show the suggested mappings to the groups of drugs that UC1 and UC2 are interested in. If a variable (drug) of interest cannot be represented by one concept in the OMOP vocabularies, multiple lines can be found.

Table 5.3 includes the drug data necessary to calculate the VIS score for UC1. The VIS score calculation also requires specific units that can be found in the same table.

Table 5.3 VIS score medications

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
dobutamine	1337720	dobutamine	Drug
dopamine	1337860	dopamine	Drug
milrinone	1368671	milrinone	Drug
epinephrine	1343916	epinephrine	Drug
vasopressin	1507835	vasopressin	Drug

norepinephrin	1321341	norepinephrin	Drug
	9688	microgram per kilogram per minute	Unit

When using the table above to populate the OMOP CDM Drug_exposure table: the conceptId indicates the specific code that should be mapped to the drug_concept_id field. The specific dose of the drug given will be mapped to the quantity field. The concept for the unit can be mapped to the dose_unit_source_value field. The vasoactive infusion start datetime must be mapped to the drug_exposure_start_date field, and the end datetime of the infusion must be mapped to the drug_exposure_end_date. In this way, the information regarding the drug, dose, units and start and end timepoints are recorded and can be used within the VIS score calculation.

Both UC1 and UC2 are interested in the use of Inotropes and Vasopressins. Therefore, both use cases can approach the standardization of the following drug data in the same way.

Table 5.4 Inotropes and vasopressors

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Dobutamine	1337720	Dobutamine	Drug
Dopamine	1337860	Dopamine	Drug

Milrinone	1368671	Milrinone	Drug
Epinephrine	1343916	Epinephrine	Drug
Vasopressin	1507835	Vasopressin	Drug
Norepinephrine	1321341	norepinephrine	Drug
Ephedrine	1143374	Ephedrine	Drug
Terlipressin	19119253	Terlipressin	Drug
Levosimendan	40173184	Levosimendan	Drug
Isoproterenol	1183554	Isoproterenol	Drug
Phenylephrine	1135766	Phenylephrine	Drug

For UC2, a list of immunosuppressant medications and non-drug source values were given, with the OMOP mappings can be found in Table 5.5.

Table 5.5 Immunosuppressants

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Prednisolone	1550557	Prednisolone	Drug
Dexamethasone	1518254	Dexamethasone	Drug
Hydrocortisone	975125	Hydrocortisone	Drug
Methylprednisolone	1506270	Methylprednisolone	Drug
Chemotherapy	4273629	Chemotherapy	Procedure
Monoclonal Antibodies	21603754	Monoclonal Antibodies	Drug

The following medications prednisolone, dexamethasone, hydrocortisone, and methylprednisolone are the only drugs included in the source variable list and should be mapped to the OMOP CDM Drug exposure table. If the immunosuppressor source value is chemotherapy, this should be mapped to the OMOP CDM Procedure occurrence table. The reason for the different tables is due to the different domains the OMOP concepts are from. Regarding the start and stop dates as before, these should be mapped to the start and end date fields of the respective OMOP tables. A final note about the Monoclonal Antibodies. The Drug or Procedure domain for the OMOP vocabularies includes specific codes for each antibody. The suggested concept is an ATC classification code that should be used as a reference to the drug group, but if the specific drugs are present in the source these should be mapped individually to the OMOP CDM Drug exposure table.

For UC2, a list of antibiotic medication was given and can be found in Table 5.6 below.

Table 5.6 Antibiotic Medication

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Penicillin	1728416	penicillin G	Drug
Ampicillin	1717327	ampicillin	Drug
Amoxicillin clavulanate	1713332	amoxicillin	Drug
	1759842	clavulanate	Drug
Amoxicillin	1713332	amoxicillin	Drug

Oxacillin	1724703	oxacillin	Drug
Piperacillin-Tazobactam	1746114	Piperacillin	Drug
	1741122	tazobactam	Drug
Cefazolin	1771162	cefazolin	Drug
Cefuroxime	1778162	cefuroxime	Drug
Cefotaxime	1774470	cefotaxime	Drug
Cefadroxil	1769535	cefadroxil	Drug
Ceftazidime	1776684	Ceftazidime	Drug
Ceftazidime-Avibactam	1776684	Ceftazidime	Drug
	46221507	avibactam	Drug
Cefepime	1748975	cefepime	Drug

Ceftolozane-Tazovactam	45892599	Ceftolozane	Drug
	1741122	tazobactam	Drug
Ertapenem	1717963	ertapenem	Drug
Imipenem	1778262	imipenem	Drug
Meropenem	1709170	meropenem	Drug
Teicoplanin	19078399	Teicoplanin	Drug
Vancomycin	1707687	Vancomycin	Drug
Gentamicin	45892419	Gentamicin	Drug
Amikacin	1790868	Amikacin	Drug
Tobramycin	902722	Tobramycin	Drug
Erythromycin	1746940	Erythromycin	Drug

Clarithromycin	1750500	Clarithromycin	Drug
Azithromycin	1734104	Azithromycin	Drug
Tetracycline	1836948	Tetracycline	Drug
Norfloxacin	1721543	Norfloxacin	Drug
Ciprofloxacin	1797513	Ciprofloxacin	Drug
Levofloxacin	1742253	Levofloxacin	Drug
Daptomycin	1786617	Daptomycin	Drug
Clindamycin	997881	Clindamycin	Drug
Fosfomycin	956653	Fosfomycin	Drug
Nitrofurantoin	920293	Nitrofurantoin	Drug
Rifampicin	1763204	Rifampicin	Drug

Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole	1705674	Trimethoprim	Drug
	1836430	Sulfamethoxazole	Drug
Linezolid	1736887	Linezolid	Drug
Mupirocin	951511	Mupirocin	Drug
Fusidic acid	19010400	Fusidate	Drug
Colistin	901845	Colistin	Drug

For UC2, the list of included antifungal medications can be found in the table below.

Table 5.7 Antifungals

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Fluconazole	1754994	fluconazole	Drug

Micafungin	19018013	micafungin	Drug
Isoavuconazole	35606695	isavuconazole	Drug
Andiulafungin	19026450	anidulafungin	Drug
Voriconazole	1714277	voriconazole	Drug

Lastly for UC2, a list of source variables representing various forms of antibiotic resistance was given and can be found in Table 5.8.

Table 5.8 Antibiotic resistance

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
MRSA	4019195	Methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus	Observation
ESBL	4257547	Extended spectrum beta-lactamase-producing bacteria	Observation
Drug-resistant	37017134	Multidrug-resistant bacteria	Observation

Multidrug-resistant	37017134	Multidrug-resistant bacteria	Observation
Clindamycin-resistant	37017134	Multidrug-resistant bacteria	Observation
	997881	clindamycin	Drug
Vancomycin-resistant	37017134	Multidrug-resistant bacteria	Observation
	1707687	vancomycin	Drug
Erythromycin-resistant	37017134	Multidrug-resistant bacteria	Observation
	1746940	erythromycin	Drug

The suggested OMOP codes listed above are either observations or drugs, this is due to the nature of the source variables.

5.2. Use case 1

5.2.1. Use case 1 description and list of variables

Clinical use case (UC) 1 will combine the retrospective outcome data from four participating hospitals (GOSH, HUS, FSJD, ERASMUS) to develop and validate a standardized, real-time ecosystem for data chelation, presentation, and monitoring of safety & quality measures, all within the federated context of the PHEMS ecosystem. The aim is to improve patient outcomes in the short term

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when compared to historical data (testing the effectiveness of the Dashboard and QIs as interventions). Thus, UC1 will contribute towards creating a benchmarking standard and promote a culture of benchmarking across pediatric cardiac institutions in Europe, enabling and facilitating the adoption of 'best-practice' across institutions (19). [\[reference to document 101094195 Annex1-Description of the action \(PartB\).pdf\]](#)

5.2.2. Semantic mappings

Below there are tables with the suggested mappings of all the variables of interest UC1 has identified. There are a few remarks for these tables. Firstly, for the variables of interest that contain dates, the event has been mapped and the date will go to its respective date field of the OMOP CDM table – see section 5.1.3. The variables that are shared between the use cases are listed in section 5.1 above (link to section). If there is no appropriate mapping found, we mark the conceptId as 'unmapped'. Lastly there are a few variables that map to many concepts, one-to-many mappings. This can happen for two reasons. Firstly, the variable can be stored with additional information in the target table or record, for example a measurement will be accompanied by a unit or measurement value. Secondly, there are some procedures listed in the list of variables that could also be represented by devices. The appropriate mapping depends on how the variable will be interpreted for the analysis and will be left to the use cases to decide. Be mindful that the distinction between Devices or supplies and Procedures is often blurry, but the former domain of concepts is reserved for physical objects and exposures to those objects while the latter are more reflective of actions, often to insert or administer a Device or supply (13).

Table 5.9 Cardiac surgery - to extract all cardiothoracic surgery from EPR

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Unspecified repair of defect of interventricular septum	4199899	Closure of ventricular septal defect	Procedure
Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation	4052536	Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation	Procedure
Other specified: plastic repair of aorta	4019026	Plastic repair of aorta	Procedure
Unspecified repair of tetralogy of fallot	4019929	Repair of tetralogy of Fallot	Procedure
Repositioning of transposed great arteries	4019932	Arterial switch operation	Procedure
Creation of anastomosis to pulmonary artery from vena cava	4019237	Anastomosis of vena cava to pulmonary artery	Procedure
Primary repair of defect of atrioventricular septum NEC/repair of persistent ostium primum/repair of persistent ostium primum	40486525	Primary repair of defect of atrioventricular septum	Procedure
	4187380	Repair of ostium primum defect	Procedure

Primary repair of defect of interatrial septum NEC/repair of defect of interatrial septum using pericardial patch	4020376	Closure of defect of interatrial septum using pericardial patch	Procedure
Application of band to pulmonary artery	4049734	Banding of pulmonary artery	Procedure
Unspecified other transplantation of heart/allotransplantation of heart NEC	4336751	Allotransplant of heart	Procedure
	4137127	Transplantation of heart	Procedure
Open implantation of ventricular assist device	4139214	Open implantation of cardiac ventricular assist device	Procedure
Total cavopulmonary connection with extracardiac inferior caval vein topulmonary artery conduit	44789857	Total cavopulmonary connection with extracardiac inferior caval vein to pulmonary artery conduit	Procedure
Implantation of cardiac pacemaker system NEC	4144921	Implantation of cardiac pacemaker	Procedure
Aortopulmonary reconstruction with systemic to pulmonary arterial shunt	44793133	Aortopulmonary reconstruction with systemic to pulmonary arterial shunt	Procedure
Unspecified correction of total anomalous pulmonary venous connection	4017751	Repair of total anomalous pulmonary venous connection	Procedure

Other specified other operations on ventricles of heart	44510968	Other specified other operations on ventricles of heart	Procedure
Revision of cardiac conduit nec/creation of valved conduit between Right ventricle of heart and Pulmonary artery/replacement of valved cardiac conduit/ replacement of pulmonary valve nec	4020506	Creation of valved conduit between right ventricle of heart and pulmonary artery	Procedure
	4178479	Replacement of valved cardiac conduit	Procedure
	4019950	Revision of valved cardiac conduit	Procedure
	4339184	Replacement of pulmonary valve	Procedure
Correction of persistent sinus venosus	4020508	Repair of sinus venosus	Procedure
Release of vascular ring of aorta	4019028	Release of vascular ring of aorta	Procedure
Repair of defect of interventricular septum using prosthetic patch/unspecified repair of defect of interventricular septum	4232476	Repair of ventricular septal defect with prosthesis	Procedure
Aortic root pulmonary valve autograft with right vent to pulmonary artery valved conduit/ aortic root pulmonary valve autograft with right vent to pulmonary artery aortoventriculoplasty	44790415	Aortic root replacement using pulmonary valve autograft with right ventricle to pulmonary artery valved conduit and aortoventriculoplasty	Procedure

Repair of subaortic stenosis	4018747	Operations on the left ventricular outflow tract	Procedure
Unspecified creation of shunt to pulmonary artery from subclavian artery using interposition tube pr	4019233	Creation of shunt from subclavian artery to pulmonary artery using interposition tube prosthesis	Procedure
Closure of patent ductus arteriosus NEC	4050114	Closure of ductus arteriosus with clip	Procedure
Removal of band from pulmonary artery	4021725	Removal of band from pulmonary artery	Procedure
Aortic valve repair NEC	4312194	Repair of heart valve	Procedure
Plastic repair of aorta and end to end anastomosis of aorta	4020812	Plastic repair of aorta and end-to-end anastomosis of aorta	Procedure
Repair of double outlet right ventricle	4049979	Repair of double outlet right ventricle	Procedure
Correction of partial anomalous pulmonary venous drainage	4018441	Repair of partial anomalous pulmonary venous connection	Procedure
Open aortic valvotomy	4020520	Open aortic valvotomy	Procedure
Other specified : repair of pulmonary artery	4018926	Repair of pulmonary artery	Procedure

Plication of diaphragm	4217615	Plication of diaphragm	Procedure
Relief of left ventricular outflow tract obstruction	44790092	Relief of left ventricular outflow tract obstruction	Procedure
Tricuspid valve repair NEC	4293619	Repair of tricuspid valve	Procedure
Repair of tetralogy of fallot using transannular patch	4308136	Complete repair of tetralogy of Fallot with transannular patch	Procedure
Replacement of mitral valve NEC	4203153	Replacement of mitral valve	Procedure
Transposition of coronary artery NEC	4296790	Transposition of coronary artery	Procedure

Table 5.10 Cardiac radiology procedures

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
US transthoracic echocardiogram/ us transthoracic echocardiogram (pre- admission)/ US transthoracic echocardiogram (sedated)	4335825	Transthoracic echocardiography	Procedure

XR chest	4163872	Plain chest X-ray	Procedure
US transoesophageal echocardiogram (toe)	4019824	Transesophageal echocardiography	Procedure
XR abdomen	4264477	Diagnostic radiography of abdomen	Procedure
US cranial contents	4083106	US scan of head	Procedure
24h holter monitor	45764527	Electrocardiographic Holter analyzer	Device
	4140473	Holter extended electrocardiographic recording	Procedure
US abdomen and pelvis/ US abdomen	4305221	US scan of abdomen and pelvis	Procedure
	4261497	Ultrasonography of abdomen	Procedure
MRI cardiac complex congenital	44802640	MRI study for cardiac congenital anomaly	Procedure
EEG routine portable	4205144	Portable electroencephalogram	Procedure
Epicardial echocardiogram	4203365	Epicardial echocardiography	Procedure

CT thorax with contrast	4327032	CT of thorax with contrast	Procedure
IR PICC line insertion	4322380	Insertion of peripherally inserted central catheter	Procedure
Event monitor	45765560	Cardiovascular monitor	Device
CT heart with contrast/ CT cardiac angiogram coronary/ CT cardiac gated with contrast	4306317	CT angiography of coronary artery with contrast	Procedure
IR tunnelled central venous line insertion	40482732	Insertion of tunneled venous catheter	Procedure
Cardiopulmonary exercise test (CPET)	40492338	Cardiopulmonary exercise test	Procedure
US thorax and pleural cavity	4093436	Ultrasonography of thorax	Procedure
	4329508	Ultrasonography of pleural cavity	Procedure
MRI head	4082979	MRI of head	Procedure
CT head	4125350	CT of head	Procedure
US urinary tract	4125530	US urinary tract	Procedure

Pacemaker/ICD interrogation (in clinic)/ pacemaker/ICD interrogation (other)	40488431	Interrogation of cardiac pacemaker	Procedure
US vocal cord	44813863	Ultrasonography of vocal cord	Procedure
Pacemaker/ICD device check - remote patient initiated	4235141	Check artificial pacemaker	Procedure
Pacemaker/ICD device check - remote device initiated	4235141	Check artificial pacemaker	Procedure
IR bronchoscopy	4032404	Bronchoscopy	Procedure
FL video swallow	4345925	Videofluoroscopy swallow	Procedure
IR bronchogram	4312208	Contrast bronchogram	Procedure
XR chest and abdomen	4169275	X-ray of chest and abdomen	Procedure
Exercise test (non-CPET)	4065416	Exercise tolerance test	Procedure
US doppler renal both	4167052	Doppler ultrasonography of kidney	Procedure

US neck	4083108	US scan of neck	Procedure
US doppler jugular vein both	40489841	Doppler ultrasonography of jugular vein	Procedure
EEG routine	4181917	Electroencephalogram	Procedure
US diaphragmatic region	4303522	US scan of diaphragm	Procedure
US doppler groin both	35622931	Doppler ultrasound	Procedure
	4167029	Ultrasonography of inguinal region	Procedure
IR tunnelled central venous line removal	42873079	Removal of tunneled central venous catheter	Procedure
US doppler	35622931	Doppler ultrasound	Procedure
US doppler lower limb veins both	4335392	Doppler ultrasonography of vein of lower limb	Procedure
MRI head with contrast	4197203	MRI of head with contrast	Procedure
FL nasojejunal feeding tube	36676722	Nasojejunal feeding tube	Device

Nerve conduction study and EMG	4198105	Nerve conduction study	Procedure
	4099523	Surface EMG	Procedure
FL bronchogram	4099738	Bilateral bronchography	Procedure
XR whole spine	4196341	Radiography of spine	Procedure
US doppler vein lower limb right	42535333	Doppler ultrasonography of vein of right lower limb	Procedure
MRA head	4167390	Magnetic resonance angiography of vascular structure of head	Procedure
MRA head and neck	45765718	Magnetic resonance angiography of head and neck	Procedure
Video telemetry acute	4102081	Video EEG	Procedure
Exercise test for S-ICD screening	4062739	Exercise status screening	Measurement
MRI spine whole	4082839	MRI of spine	Procedure
CT thorax	4058335	CT of chest	Procedure

US soft tissue	4085452	Ultrasonography of soft tissue mass	Procedure
US doppler groin right	4183725	Doppler device	Device
	42535019	Ultrasonography of right groin and right scrotum	Procedure
XR orthopantomogram full	4233227	Orthopantomogram	Procedure

Table 5.11 Cardiac length of stay

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
ICU admission (start datetime and end datetime)	4123933	Admission to pediatric intensive care unit	Observation
HDU admission (start datetime and end datetime)	4161811	Admission to high dependency unit	Observation
Cardiology ward admission (start datetime and end datetime)	36675203	Admission to pediatric cardiology department	Observation

Total hospital admission (start datetime and end datetime)	8715	Hospital admission	Observation
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Table 5.12 Additional

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Outpatient appointments start datetime, end datetime	9202	Outpatient Visit	Visit
Outpatient appointment type (telephone/ clinic visit etc.)	5083	Telehealth	Visit
Outpatient specialty	32577	Physician	Provider
Diagnoses	4234469	Diagnosis	Observation
Systolic blood pressure	4152194	Systolic blood pressure	Measurement
	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit

Pupillary reaction	4209008	Pupillary function	Observation
PaCO2	3027946	Carbon dioxide [Partial pressure] in Arterial blood	Measurement
	44777602	kilopascal	Unit
	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
FiO2	42869590	Oxygen/Gas total [Pure volume fraction] Inhaled gas	Measurement
	8554	percent	Unit
Mechanical ventilation	40493026	Mechanical ventilator	Device
Base Excess	4030916	Base excess	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Elective ICU admission	4123933	Admission to pediatric intensive care unit	Observation
Reason for ICU admission: (Main reason for ICU admission is not recovery from surgery or a procedure, Recovery from a bypass cardiac	44803020	Primary reason for admission	Observation

procedure, recovery from a non-bypass cardiac procedure, recovery from non-cardiac procedure)			
Low Risk Diagnoses: None, asthma, bronchiolitis, croup, obstructive sleep apnea, diabetic ketoacidosis, seizure disorder	443727	Diabetic ketoacidosis	Condition
	442588	Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome	Condition
	317009	Asthma	Condition
	4165112	Bronchiolitis	Condition
	260134	Croup	Condition
	4029498	Seizure disorder	Condition
High Risk Diagnoses: (None, spontaneous cerebral hemorrhage, cardiomyopathy or myocarditis, hypoplastic left heart syndrome, neurodegenerative disorder, necrotizing enterocolitis)	43530727	Spontaneous cerebral hemorrhage	Condition
	321319	Cardiomyopathy	Condition
	314383	Myocarditis	Condition
	440207	Hypoplastic left heart syndrome	Condition

	4213310	Degenerative disease of the central nervous system	Condition
	201957	Necrotizing enterocolitis in fetus OR newborn	Condition
Very High Risk Diagnoses: None, cardiac arrest preceding ICU admission, severe combined immune deficiency, leukemia or lymphoma after first induction, bone marrow transplant recipient, liver failure	42537745	Bone marrow transplant present	Observation
	321042	Cardiac arrest	Condition
	4124462	None	Meas Value
	29783	Severe combined immunodeficiency disease	Condition
	317510	Leukemia	Condition
	432571	Malignant lymphoma	Condition
	4245975	Hepatic failure	Condition

Table 5.13 Laboratory test results (copied from UC_2 SEPSIS - reusing variables, except pH/pCO₂/bicarbonate which was further split into venous / arterial)

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Immature WBC count	4298431	White blood cell count	Measurement
	8647	per microliter	Unit
Neutrophil count	37393856	Neutrophil count	Measurement
	3007670	Neutrophil Ab [Units/volume] in Serum	Measurement
	8647	per microliter	Unit
Hemoglobin	40762351	Hemoglobin [Moles/volume] in Blood	Measurement
	8713	gram per deciliter	Unit
	8636	gram per liter	Unit
Platelet count	37393863	Platelet count	Measurement

	8647	per microliter	Unit
Hematocrit	3009542	Hematocrit [Volume Fraction] of Blood	Measurement
	8554	percent	Unit
INR prothrombin time	3034426	Prothrombin time (PT)	Measurement
	8555	second	Unit
Lactate	3047181	Lactate [Moles/volume] in Blood	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Creatinine	3051825	Creatinine [Mass/volume] in Blood	Measurement
	8840	milligram per deciliter	Unit
	8749	micromole per liter	Unit
Albumin	3024561	Albumin [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement

	8713	gram per deciliter	Unit
	8636	gram per liter	Unit
Blood urea nitrogen	40762632	Urea nitrogen [Moles/volume] in Blood	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Glucose	3013826	Glucose [Moles/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Bilirubin	3006140	Bilirubin total [Moles/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	8749	micromole per liter	Unit
Sodium	3019550	Sodium [Moles/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Potassium	3005456	Potassium [Moles/volume] in Blood	Measurement

	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Magnesium	3033836	Magnesium [Moles/volume] in Blood	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Chloride	3018572	Chloride [Moles/volume] in Blood	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Calcium	3015377	Calcium [Moles/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Phosphate	3003458	Phosphate [Moles/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
CRP	3020460	C reactive protein [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	8751	milligram per liter	Unit

ALT	3006923	Alanine aminotransferase [Enzymatic activity/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	8645	unit per liter	Unit
AST	3013721	Aspartate aminotransferase [Enzymatic activity/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	8645	unit per liter	Unit
pH (venous)	37392672	Blood venous pH	Measurement
pH (arterial)	37399161	Blood arterial pH	Measurement
pCO2 (venous)	3021447	Carbon dioxide [Partial pressure] in Venous blood	Measurement
	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
	44777602	kilopascal	Unit
pCO2 (arterial)	3027946	Carbon dioxide [Partial pressure] in Arterial blood	Measurement
	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit

pO2 (venous)	3024354	Oxygen [Partial pressure] in Venous blood	Measurement
	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
pO2 (arterial)	3027801	Oxygen [Partial pressure] in Arterial blood	Measurement
	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
Bicarbonate (venous)	3027273	Bicarbonate [Moles/volume] in Venous blood	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Bicarbonate (arterial)	3008152	Bicarbonate [Moles/volume] in Arterial blood	Measurement
	8753	millimole per liter	Unit

Table 5.14 Cardiac complications

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain

ICU ward stay	4123933	Admission to pediatric intensive care unit	Observation
CVL infections	42537043	CLABSI - central line associated bloodstream infection	Condition
Low cardiac output state (LCOS) - ECMO	4221102	Cardiac output	Measurement
	4052536	Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation	Procedure
LCOS - renal support (CVVH/ PD)	4051330	Continuous venovenous hemofiltration	Procedure
	4324124	Peritoneal dialysis	Procedure
	4185565	Low cardiac output syndrome	Condition
LCOS - Cardiac arrest	321042	Cardiac arrest	Condition
	4185565	Low cardiac output syndrome	Condition
LCOS - NEC requiring treatment	4185565	Low cardiac output syndrome	Condition
Neurological injury - infarction	443454	Cerebral infarction	Condition

Neurological injury - seizure	377091	Seizure	Condition
Neurological injury - intracranial haemorrhage/ intracranial bleeding	439847	Intracranial hemorrhage	Condition
Surgical injury - Blood Loss	4308537	Injury to blood vessel during surgery	Condition
Surgical injury - Chylothorax	4306136	Chylothorax	Condition
Surgical injury - Reexplore for bleeding	4295705	Exploratory incision	Procedure
	437312	Bleeding	Condition
	442019	Complication of procedure	Condition

Table 5.15 Vital signs

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Age-dependent HR	4239408	Heart rate	Measurement

	8483	counts per minute	Unit
Age-dependent RR	4313591	Respiratory rate	Measurement
	8483	counts per minute	Unit
SBP (Systolic Blood Pressure)	4152194	Systolic blood pressure	Measurement
	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
DBP (Dyastolic Blood Pressure)	4154790	Diastolic blood pressure	Measurement
	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
SpO2	4096101	Measurement of oxygen saturation at periphery	Measurement
	8554	Percent	Unit

Table 5.16 Other variables proposed by HSJD Clinical

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM
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	conceptId	concept name	domain
Weight	3025315	Body weight	Measurement
	9529	kilogram	Unit
Height	607590	Body height	Measurement
	8582	centimeter	Unit
Body Surface Area (BSA) - Combination of weight and height	4201235	Body surface area	Measurement
	8617	square meter	Unit
Extracardiac anomalies - diagnoses	0	Unmapped	NaN
Cardiac surgeries (Interventions)	4275564	Operation on heart	Procedure

Table 5.17 Other variables proposed by HSJD Surgery

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM
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	conceptId	concept name	domain
Aristotle's score of surgery	0	Unmapped	NaN
STAT/EACTS score of surgery	40490494	Society of Thoracic Surgeons risk calculator	Measurement
Surgery start datetime, end datetime	4301351	Surgical procedure	Procedure
Cardiac bypass start datetime, end datetime	4336464	Coronary artery bypass graft	Procedure
Cross-clamping start datetime, end datetime	4201547	Placement of arterial cross clamp	Procedure
Deep hypothermic circulatory arrest start datetime, end datetime	44790138	Induced circulatory arrest	Procedure
Antegrade Cerebral Perfusion start datetime, end datetime	4272324	Cardiopulmonary bypass operation	Procedure
Extubation event	4150627	Removal of endotracheal tube	Procedure

Table 5.18 Other variables proposed by HSJD Hospitalisation

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Admission reason	44803020	Primary reason for admission	Observation
ventilation	0	Unmapped	NaN
Vasoactive infusion start datetime, end datetime	42539650	Administration of intravenous vasoactive drug	Procedure
Type of vasoactive infusion	0	Unmapped	NaN
Dose of vasoactive infusion (rate - mcg/kg/hr)	794078	vasoactive intestinal peptide	Drug
VIS score of vasoactive infusion	0	Unmapped	NaN
Postop central venous catheter in/start datetime, out/end datetime	4179206	Central venous catheter	Device
Total ventilation start datetime, end datetime	0	Unmapped	NaN
Invasive Mechanical Ventilation LOS	37158404	Invasive mechanical ventilation	Procedure

Non-Invasive Mechanical Ventilation LOS	4177224	Non-invasive ventilation	Procedure
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Table 5.19 Other variables proposed by HSJD Complications

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
intubation	4202832	Intubation	Procedure
Cardiac surgeries (interventions)	4275564	Operation on heart	Procedure
Sternum reopening (procedure undertaken)	4044892	Procedure on sternum	Procedure
Vocal Cord Dysfunction	4046868	Vocal cord dysfunction	Condition
Diaphragmatic Paralysis	4275136	Paralysis of diaphragm	Condition
Pneumothorax	253796	Pneumothorax	Condition
Tracheostomy	44783799	Exteriorization of trachea	Procedure

Arrhythmia diagnosis (tachyarrhythmia, bradyarrhythmia, atrial, ventricular etc.)	44784217	Cardiac arrhythmia	Condition
	315643	Tachyarrhythmia	Condition
	4228448	Bradyarrhythmia	Condition
	4068155	Atrial arrhythmia	Condition
	4185572	Ventricular arrhythmia	Condition
Drugs administered; Arrhythmia therapy (drugs): IV anthyarritemics (ivabradine, amiodarone, flecainide)	46234437	ivabradine	Drug
	1309944	amiodarone	Drug
	1354860	flecainide	Drug
Arrhythmia therapy (procedures): Cardioversion, Rapid atrial pacing, temporary pacing, permanent pacing)	4353741	Cardioversion	Procedure
	4117045	Atrial overdrive pacing	Procedure
	4049398	Temporary cardiac pacemaker procedure	Procedure

	4051940	Permanent cardiac pacemaker procedure	Procedure
Listed for heart transplantation	609312	Awaiting transplantation of heart	Observation

5.2.3. Values to get the derived variables from

There are some variables in UC1 that should not be mapped as such in the target model but rather be extracted by querying the OMOP CDM tables. Two distinct types can be identified.

The first is the time-dependent variables. For example, variable 'Age dependent heart rate'. The term to map to OMOP will be the actual measurement of the heart rate for the patient together with the time that said measurement was taken. The age part of the variable would be a simple calculation from the time of the event and the date of birth, where the latter should be available at the CDM Person table. Another use of the desired variable might have to do also with specific ranges serving as normal. If that is the case the ranges can be included in the CDM Measurement table and more specifically at the range_high, range_low fields. This can then be used to indicate the normal.

Secondly there are variables that are not specifying an event but aim to count and group events. An example is the variable 'Outpatient specialty'. In the target model, the different specialties a patient has seen should be mapped individually, and the count of the different visits can be a query of the relevant records.

5.2.4. Variables already in OMOP

In the variable spreadsheet there are codes suggested by UC1 for "24h Holter monitor", "Albumin", "Age-dependent HR" and "Age-dependent RR". Additionally, HUS has provided a list of OMOP codes that their OMOP CDM uses. A comparison of the codes suggested by the Hyve and the ones available in the spreadsheet are listed below (5). The ones in red indicate non-standard concepts and should not be used. Note that when there is an agreement between HUS's and The Hyve's mapping, this variable is not listed.

Table 5.20 Target concept comparison

PHEMS variable of interest	Suggested by	OMOP CDM			
		conceptId	concept name	domain	
24h Holter monitor	The Hyve	45764527	Electrocardiographic Holter analyzer	Device	
		4140473	Holter extended electrocardiographic recording	Procedure	
	UC1	4313572	Electrocardiographic monitor and recorder	Device	
		447775566	score	Unit	
	HUS	4098508	24 Hour ECG	Procedure	
		4065278	Ambulatory ECG	Procedure	
	<p>Comment: The concept code suggested by the Hyve specifies the 'Holter' device. The Hyve also suggests two mappings (one to procedure and one to device) depending on how the variable is treated and what is available in the source data. If the focus is on how the data was collected, the device exposure table is more suitable. If the procedure itself is important, then the procedure occurrence table should be used.</p> <p>Comment HUS: at HUS device data is not available, only the procedure</p>				

Albumin	The Hyve	4017497	Albumin measurement, serum	Measurement
	UC1	44803020	Primary reason for admission	Observation
	Comment: The concept code suggested by UC1 here is not relevant to the variable.			
Age-dependent HR	The Hyve	4239408	Heart rate	Measurement
		8483	counts per minute	Unit
	UC1	44803020	Primary reason for admission	Observation
		8581	heartbeat	Unit
	Comment: The observation concept code suggested by UC1 here is not relevant to the variable. And the second concept 'heartbeat' although standard is a unit. The Hyve suggests mapping this to the Measurement heart rate with unit_as_concept_id as the unit above.			
Age-dependent RR	The Hyve	4313591	Respiratory rate	Measurement
		8483	counts per minute	Unit
	UC1	4313591	Respiratory rate	Measurement

		4239408	Heart rate	Measurement
	Comment: The concept codes suggested by UC1 here are not standard concepts in the latest vocabulary.			
Sternum reopening (procedure undertaken)	The Hyve	4044892	Procedure on sternum	Procedure
	HUS	4231751	Median sternotomy	Procedure
Unspecified repair of tetralogy of Fallot	The Hyve/ HUS	4019929	Repair of tetralogy of Fallot	Procedure
	HUS	4308136	Complete repair of tetralogy of Fallot with transannular patch	Procedure
	Comment: The concept code suggested here is more specific than the use case variable. The variable reads 'unspecified' but the concept used at HUS is a 'complete repair ... with transannular patch'. Comment HUS: An error made in haste. We use same concept id for unspecified			
Primary repair of defect of interatrial septum NEC/ repair of defect of interatrial septum using pericardial patch	The Hyve	4020376	Closure of defect of interatrial septum using pericardial patch	Procedure
	HUS	4219986	Closure of patent foramen ovale	Procedure

	<p>Comment: The concept code suggested here by the Hyve is specific to the variable of interest. The HUS suggested concept is a more general concept and missing the 'using pericardial patch' information.</p> <p>Comment HUS: Closure of patent foramen ovale is only one of ASD procedures that we have omopised.</p>			
Replacement of mitral valve NEC	The Hyve	4203153	Replacement of mitral valve	Procedure
	HUS	4160418	Mechanical prosthetic mitral valve replacement	Procedure
		4173712	Replacement of mitral valve with tissue graft	Procedure
	<p>Comment: The choice for this variable is dependent on the source codes for each site. The variable is generic and the Hyve chose the concept to be the same. The HUS suggested concept_ids make sense to be used only if the source data is available in the same granularity at for all the sites. Then it should also be taken into account that the UC variable is found in more than one concept.</p>			
US transthoracic echocardiogram/ us transthoracic echocardiogram (pre- admission)/ US transthoracic echocardiogram (sedated)	The Hyve	4335825	Transthoracic echocardiography	Procedure
	HUS	4230911	Echocardiography	Procedure

	Comment: The concept suggested by HUS is missing the anatomic site information the UC variable includes.			
XR chest	The Hyve/ HUS	4163872	Plain chest X-ray	Procedure
	HUS	4056836	Standard chest X-ray	Procedure
	Comment: HUS has indicated that both concepts are used for the chest X-ray procedure. This would make sense if the source data the detail recorded, plain vs standard. The Hyve team doesn't see a reason to split the two only from the UC1 variable selection.			
US cranial contents	The Hyve	4083106	US scan of head	Procedure
	HUS	2789561	Ultrasonography of Brain	Procedure
	<p>Comment: The UC variable of interest is cranial and can include more than the brain that is suggested by HUS. On the other hand, the variable suggested by the Hyve is wider and includes additional structures like the facial bones. The correct concept to use depends on the UC1 interest.</p> <p>Comment2: HUS has provided additional information that their source data include only ultrasound of the brain/cranial.</p>			
US abdomen and pelvis/ US abdomen	The Hyve	4305221	US scan of abdomen and pelvis	Procedure

	The Hyve/HUS	4261497	Ultrasonography of abdomen	Procedure
	Comment: The UC variable includes two different concepts in OMOP and ideally should map to both.			
MRI cardiac complex congenital	The Hyve	44802640	MRI study for cardiac congenital anomaly	Procedure
	HUS	4082987	Cardiac MRI	Procedure
	Comment: The concepts are theoretically different if you take into account that the variable refers to children. The choice depends on the data representation. If there is one concept used for adults and children, then the concept suggested by HUS is a good choice. However, if the distinction is there it is advisable to use the Hyve suggested concept. Comment HUS: At least for HUS this is the closest.			
Epicardial echocardiogram	The Hyve	4203365	Epicardial echocardiography	Procedure
	HUS	4230911	Echocardiography	Procedure
	Comment: The concept suggested by HUS is missing the specific anatomic site information, therefore the Hyve suggests a different concept.			
CT thorax with contrast	The Hyve	4327032	CT of thorax with contrast	Procedure

	HUS	4058335	CT of chest	Procedure
	Comment: The Hyve suggested concept is the same as the UC variable whilst the HUS suggested concept is more generic.			
CT heart with contrast/ CT cardiac angiogram coronary/ CT cardiac gated with contrast	The Hyve	4306317	CT angiography of coronary artery with contrast	Procedure
	HUS	4083211	Cardiac CT	Procedure
	Comment: slightly broader concept. Comment HUS: We actually use 4142645 and 4148369 as well but these don't specify CT			
IR tunnelled central venous line insertion	The Hyve	40482732	Insertion of tunneled venous catheter	Procedure
	HUS	4052415	Central venous cannula insertion via subclavian vein	Procedure
		4322380	Insertion of peripherally inserted central catheter	Procedure
		4116186	Central venous cannula insertion via jugular vein	Procedure

	Comment: The HUS concepts used would be useful to keep if the source further detailed information. The four concepts above share the common ancestor 'Insertion of central venous catheter, 37156341'. Given the UC1 variable of interest the Hyve team believes the suggested concept is the most appropriate. However, in the analysis when concept sets are created the higher concept might be better to use with all its descendants.			
US thorax and pleural cavity	The Hyve/ HUS	4093436	Ultrasonography of thorax	Procedure
	The Hyve	4329508	Ultrasonography of pleural cavity	Procedure
Pacemaker/ICD interrogation (in clinic)/ pacemaker/ICD interrogation (other)	The Hyve	40488431	Interrogation of cardiac pacemaker	Procedure
	HUS	4049403	Maintenance procedure for cardiac pacemaker system	Procedure
	Comment: Based on language only interrogation and maintenance are different. The Hyve team is not aware, if in medical terms, the two would be equivalent therefore suggests the most closely related concept.			
IR bronchoscopy	The Hyve	4032404	Bronchoscopy	Procedure
	HUS	4233305	Endoscopic ultrasonography of bronchus	Procedure

	<p>Comment: The HUS suggested concept is a more specific procedure than The UC1 variable. The 'ultrasonography' part is additional information to the type of bronchoscopy.</p> <p>Comment HUS: Noticed today that this is not correct. For bronchoscopy we use 4311817 or 4262301 which are probably descendants of the Hyve proposed</p>			
FL video swallow	The Hyve	4345925	Videofluoroscopy swallow	Procedure
	HUS	4199943	Contrast swallow	Procedure
	<p>Comment: This concept should be reviewed by a physician. As far as the Hyve understands the videofluoroscopy swallow can be performed with any contrast material, but the contrast swallow is always barium. A clinical expertise on how the two related is essential here and is expected to change at the review by WP4 of this document.</p>			
US doppler groin both	The Hyve	35622931	Doppler ultrasound	Procedure
		36684416	Ultrasonography of groin and scrotum	Procedure
	HUS	4167029	Ultrasonography of inguinal region	Procedure
	<p>Comment: This concept should be reviewed by a clinician. The Hyve team could not determine a concept that has both the 'doppler' information together with the anatomic site information. Could the Ultrasonography be enough information without the Doppler specification? A clinical expertise on how the two related is essential here and is expected to change at the review by WP4 of this document.</p>			

	Comment HUS: I would suggest using only ultrasonography, at least in HUS the radiologists use Doppler without specific request			
MRA head and neck	The Hyve	45765718	Magnetic resonance angiography of head and neck	Procedure
	HUS	4276939	Angiography of artery of head, neck and/or brain	Procedure
	Comment: The Hyve suggested concept represents the variable as indicated by UC1. The HUS suggested concept introduces a new anatomical site and misses the magnetic nature of angiography.			
MRI spine whole	The Hyve/ HUS	4082839	MRI of spine	Procedure
	HUS	40493263	MRI of spinal cord	Procedure
	<p>Comment: The variable of interest indicates the spine as a whole and the spinal cord represents a specific part of the spine. The whole spine also includes the vertebrae, facet joints, intervertebral disks, nerves and soft tissues. Looking at the hierarchy of the HUS suggested concepts we see that the whole spine is not represented here. However, if the source data information is specific, we advise to use the concept as it is. The Hyve suggested concept is the parent of it.</p> <p>Comment HUS: HUS proposal: Let's use this and disregard spinal cord</p>			

Immature WBC count	The Hyve	4298431	White blood cell count	Measurement
		8647	per microliter	Unit
	HUS	3032352	Blasts [# / volume] in Cerebral spinal fluid	Measurement
	<p>Comment: The HUS suggested concept is specifying the anatomical site the measurement was taken from making it more specific than the UC1 variable of interest.</p> <p>Comment HUS: This is not correct and can be disregarded.</p>			
pH (venous)	The Hyve	37392672	Blood venous pH	Measurement
	HUS	3000991	Gas panel - Venous blood	Measurement
	<p>Comment: The next three venous variables are represented by the same concept in the HUS data. This would allow confusion between the measurements taken, and the Hyve team would suggest splitting them into individual concepts.</p> <p>Comment HUS: Should be: 3012544 Agree with Hyve and we have more specific ids for these. Just didn't have enough time to dig this from the data lake.</p>			
pH (arterial)	The Hyve	37399161	Blood arterial pH	Measurement

	HUS	4315395	Rhodotorula rubra	Observation
	<p>Comment: The next three arterial variables are represented by the same concept in the HUS data. This seems like a mistake as the suggested concept is a fungus.</p> <p>Comment HUS: Should be: 3019977. Probably an error while pasting. See above</p>			
pCO2 (venous)	The Hyve	3021447	Carbon dioxide [Partial pressure] in Venous blood	Measurement
		8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
	HUS	3000991	Gas panel - Venous blood	Measurement
	<p>Comment: See comment for pH (venous)</p> <p>Comment HUS: HUS actually uses the concept suggested by the Hyve. The concept above can be disregarded.</p>			
pCO2 (arterial)	The Hyve	3027946	Carbon dioxide [Partial pressure] in Arterial blood	Measurement
		8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
	HUS	4315395	Rhodotorula rubra	Observation

	Comment: See comment for pH (arterial)			
pO2 (venous)	The Hyve	3024354	Oxygen [Partial pressure] in Venous blood	Measurement
		8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
	HUS	3000991	Gas panel - Venous blood	Measurement
	Comment: See comment for pH (venous)			
pO2 (arterial)	The Hyve	3027801	Oxygen [Partial pressure] in Arterial blood	Measurement
		8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
	HUS	4315395	Rhodotorula rubra	Observation
	Comment: See comment for pH (arterial)			
Surgical injury - Chylothorax	The Hyve	4306136	Chylothorax	Condition
	HUS	4031202	Pseudochylothorax	Condition

	<p>Comment: The two conditions are different in medical literature, and they are characterized by different symptoms.</p> <p>Comment HUS: The source value is correct but the mapping seems to be erroneous</p>
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5.3. Use case 2

5.3.1. Use case 2 description and list of variables

Utilizing the PHEMS federated ecosystem, UC2 will acquire and use data from multiple children's hospitals to develop and train machine learning algorithms to predict sepsis in pediatric intensive care units (PICUs). The development is divided into two phases. The first phase involves validating early warning scores (PESERS). The second phase concerns the development of supervised machine-learning models with federated data.

The dataset composed for UC2 includes a thorough exploration of patient health and clinical history surrounding sepsis. There is detailed information about the patients' demographics and extensive healthcare records, such as the length of clinical stays and relevant diagnoses. Vital sign assessments and physical examination indicators are incorporated. Laboratory tests comprise the largest segment of the dataset, ranging from pathogen infections and antibiotic resistance to hematological parameters (19).

5.3.2. Semantic mappings

Below there are tables with the suggested mappings of all the variables of interest UC2 has identified. These tables are structured in the same manner and can be interpreted the same way as tables 5.9-5.19 for UC1. Additionally, UC2 measurement concepts are in specific cases accompanied by 'Meas Value' concepts. These represent categorical results of measurements, such as the "not existing", "poor", and "vigorous" Meas Value concepts proposed for pulse presences. These are to be mapped to MEASUREMENT.value_as_concept_id in the OMOP CDM. For the variables that have more than one underlying mapping, for

example Reason for Admission, one can map the general concept Reason for Admission to the observation_concept_ID, and the specific reason to the value_as_concept_id.

Note: not all laboratory test variables are covered by Table 5.24, as many variables are identical between UC1 and UC2. The remaining laboratory test variables are consequently covered in Table 5.14.

Table 5.21 Healthcare use, clinical diagnoses, and treatment procedures in the current episode

PHEMS variable of interest	Site using the unit/ SI system	OMOP CDM		
		conceptId	concept name	domain
Previous diagnosis of sepsis measure	-	1340204	History of event	Observation
	-	132797	Sepsis	Condition
Origin (external)	-	44790567	Patient transfer from hospital to hospital	Visit
Origin (internal)	-	4294886	Patient transfer, in-hospital	Observation
Reason for admission	-	44803020	Primary reason for admission	Observation
Surgical admission (non-urgent)	-	4084670	Non-urgent surgical admission	Observation
Surgical admission (urgent)	-	4123946	Admission to surgical department	Observation

Non-surgical admission	-	0	Unmapped	
Central venous catheter	-	4179206	Central venous catheter	Device
Diagnosis of chronic condition	-	443783	Chronic disease	Condition
	-	312723	Congenital heart disease	Condition
	-	201820	Diabetes mellitus	Condition
	-	255573	Chronic obstructive lung disease	Condition
Diagnosis of acute infection having the potential for progression to sepsis1+2	-	37174269	At increased risk of sepsis	Observation
	-	4271450	Acute infectious disease	Condition
Meningo-encephalitis		4322814	Meningoencephalitis	Condition
hepatitis		4243475	Acute hepatitis	Condition
pneumonia		255848	Pneumonia	Condition

meningitis		435785	meningitis	Condition
bacteremia		132736	bacteremia	Condition
viremia		133327	viremia	Condition
UTI		4331815	Acute urinary tract infection	Condition
tuberculosis		4103588	Acute tuberculosis	Condition
candidiasis		433968	Candidiasis	Condition
Diagnosis of SIRS	-	434821	Systemic inflammatory response syndrome	Condition
Diagnosis of condition producing immunodeficiency	-	4140977	Secondary immune deficiency disorder	Condition
Abcess		444202	Abscess	Condition
appendicitis		440448	Appendicitis	Condition

peritonitis		196152	Peritonitis	Condition
cellulitis		435613	Cellulitis	Condition
surgical site inflammation		4300243	Postoperative complication	Condition
injury with open wound		444187	Open wound	Condition
renal insufficiency		36716945	Renal insufficiency	Condition
endocarditis		441589	Endocarditis	Condition
miocarditis		314383	Myocarditis	Condition
necrotizing enterocolitis		44807226	Necrotising enterocolitis	Condition
Cancer		443392	Malignant neoplastic disease	Condition
cardiac arrest		321042	Cardiac arrest	Condition
organ transplant		4208341	Solid organ transplant	Procedure

acute kidney injury		197320	Acute kidney injury	Condition
immunodeficiency		433740	Immunodeficiency disorder	Condition
asplenia		45768671	Asplenia	Condition
cerebral palsy		134120	Cerebral palsy	Condition
rheumatoid arthritis		80809	Rheumatoid arthritis	Condition
sickle cell disease		22281	Sickle cell-hemoglobin SS disease	Condition
ulcerative colitis		81893	Ulcerative colitis	Condition
Crohn's disease		201606	Crohn's disease	Condition
Cushing's disease		195212	Hypercortisolism	Condition
Down's syndrome		439125	Complete trisomy 21 syndrome	Condition
mitochondrial disease		81539	Mitochondrial cytopathy	Condition

nephrotic syndrome		195314	Nephrotic syndrome	Condition
neutropenia		604243	Acquired neutropenia	Condition
Diagnosis of organ system dysfunction	-	4080011	Organ dysfunction syndrome	Condition
Antibiotics	-	4085730	Antibiotic therapy	Procedure
Antivirals	-	4140762	Antiviral therapy	Procedure
Immunosuppressors	-	4314777	Immunosuppressive therapy	Procedure
Corticoids	-	21602722	CORTICOSTEROIDS FOR SYSTEMIC USE	Procedure
Antineoplastics	-	4181511	Administration of antineoplastic agent	Procedure
Surgery previous to prediction time point	-	4301351	Surgical procedure	Procedure
Chest opening, chest drainage	-	4074689	Open drainage of pleural cavity	Procedure
Arterial blood pressure catheter	-	45758028	Arterial blood pressure catheter	Device

Peripheral IV cannulas	-	4177205	Cannulation	Procedure
Urinary catheter	-	4070667	Urinary Catheter	Device
Nasogastric/orogastric tube	-	42538045	Nasogastric/orogastric tube stylet	Device
Endotracheal tube	-	4097216	Endotracheal tube	Device
Tracheostomy	-	44783799	Exteriorization of trachea	Procedure
Invasive ventilation	-	44790095	Invasive ventilation	Procedure
Non-invasive ventilation	-	4177224	Non-invasive ventilation	Procedure
FiO2	-	42869590	Oxygen/Gas total [Pure volume fraction] Inhaled gas	Measurement
	UC2, HSJD, Erasmus, SI unit	8554	percent	Unit
	UC2, HSJD	8510	unit	Unit
	GOSH	720868	fraction	Unit

Mean Airway Pressure (MAP)	-	42527086	Mean airway pressure	Measurement
	UC2, HSJD, Erasmus	44777590	cmH2O	Unit
	Erasmus	8876	mmHg	Unit
	Erasmus	44777602	kilopascal	Unit
Oxygenation index	-	4193843	Oxygenation index measurement	Measurement
	UC2, Erasmus	8529	index	Unit
	GOSH	0	unmapped	Unit
ECMO	-	4052536	Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation	Procedure
ECMO type	-	37206603	Venovenous extracorporeal membrane oxygenation	Procedure
	-	37206601	Venoarterial extracorporeal membrane oxygenation	Procedure

Ventricular assist device (VAD)	-	4235043	Ventricular assist device	Device
Dialysis	-	4032243	Dialysis procedure	Procedure
		4051330	Continuous venovenous hemofiltration	Procedure
Peritoneal dialysis	-	4324124	Peritoneal dialysis	Procedure

Table 5.22 Vital signs

PHEMS variable of interest	Site using the unit/ SI system	OMOP CDM		
		conceptId	concept name	domain
HR	-	1004025	Heart rate	Measurement
	All sites	8483	counts per minute	Unit
RR	-	3024171	Respiratory rate	Measurement

	All sites	8483	counts per minute	Unit
Body temperature	-	3020891	Body temperature	Measurement
	All sites	586323	degree Celsius	Unit
SBP (Systolic Blood Pressure)	-	3004249	Systolic blood pressure	Measurement
	All sites	8876	mmHg	Unit
DBP (Diastolic blood pressure)	-	3012888	Diastolic blood pressure	Measurement
	All sites	8876	mmHg	Unit
SpO2	-	4096101	Measurement of oxygen saturation at periphery	Measurement
	All sites	8554	percent	Unit
Urine output	-	3014315	Urine output	Measurement
	GOSH, HUS	8587	milliliter	Unit

	UC2	44777613	milliliter per hour	Unit
	Erasmus	33014	milliliter per kilogram per 24 hours	Unit
	HUS	0	unmapped	Unit
Weight	-	3025315	Body weight	Measurement
	UC2, Erasmus	9529	kilogram	Unit
	GOSH	8504	gram	Unit

Table 5.23 Physical examination signs

PHEMS variable of interest	Site using the unit/ SI system	OMOP CDM		
		conceptId	concept name	domain
GCS	-	3032652	Glasgow Coma Scale	Measurement

Pupillary reactivity (right)	-	21490963	Right pupil Pupillary response	Measurement
	UC2	4069590	Normal	Meas value
	UC2	45879546	Sluggish	Meas value
	UC2	45880051	Unresponsive	Meas value
	Erasmus	4188539	Yes	Meas value
	Erasmus	4188540	No	Meas value
Pupillary reactivity (left)	-	21491763	Left pupil Pupillary response	Measurement
	UC2	4069590	Normal	Meas value
	UC2	45879546	Sluggish	Meas value
	UC2	45880051	Unresponsive	Meas value
	Erasmus	4188539	Yes	Meas value

	Erasmus	4188540	No	Meas value
Pupillary size (right)	-	3027214	Right pupil Diameter Auto	Measurement
	GOSH, HUS	8588	millimeter	Unit
	UC2	36310446	Constricted	Meas Value
	UC2	21499034	Dilated	Meas Value
	UC2	4116857	Medium	Meas Value
Pupillary size (left)	-	3021415	Left pupil Diameter Auto	Measurement
	GOSH, HUS	8588	millimeter	Unit
	UC2	36310446	Constricted	Meas Value
	UC2	21499034	Dilated	Meas Value
	UC2	4116857	Medium	Meas Value

Capillary refill time	-	3045676	Capillary refill [Time]	Measurement
	UC2, HSJD, Erasmus, GOSH	8555	second	Unit
Peripheral pulse (pressure)	-	4314539	Arterial pulse pressure	Measurement
	UC2, HSJD, Erasmus	4181412	Present	Meas Value
	UC2, HSJD, Erasmus	4132135	Absent	Meas Value
	HSJD	4124461	Weak	Meas Value
	HUS	8483	counts per minute	Unit
Central pulse	-	4224504	Pulse	Measurement

	UC2, HSJD, Erasmus	4181412	Present	Meas Value
	UC2, HSJD, Erasmus	4132135	Absent	Meas Value
	HSJD	4124461	Weak	Meas Value
	HUS	8483	counts per minute	Unit

Table 5.24 Laboratory test results

PHEMS variable of interest	Site using the unit/ SI system	OMOP CDM		
		conceptId	concept name	domain
Bacterial pathogen detection	-	4036356	Detection of bacteria	Measurement
Name of bacterial pathogen detected	-	432545	Bacterial infectious disease	Condition

Quantification of colonies in culture	-	4299649	Quantitative microbial culture and measurement	Measurement
	UC2	9278	colony forming unit	Unit
PCR panel	-	4196268	Polymerase chain reaction observation	Condition
Antibiotic resistance	-	44806682	Infection resistant to multiple antibiotics	Condition
Viral pathogen detection	-	440029	Viral disease	Condition
PCR panel	-	4196268	Polymerase chain reaction observation	Condition
Leukocytes	-	4212899	Total white blood count	Measurement
	UC2, GOSH, HUS	9278	billion per liter	Unit
	HSJD	0	unmapped	Unit
Thromboplastin time	-	4175016	Partial thromboplastin time, activated	Measurement

	All sites	8555	second	Unit
	HSJD	8523	ratio	Unit
D-dimer	-	37393605	D-dimer level	Measurement
	UC2, HUS	8751	milligram per liter	Unit
	Erasmus	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Fibrinogen	-	4094436	Fibrinogen measurement	Measurement
	UC2, HUS	8636	gram per liter	Unit
	Erasmus	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Blood urea nitrogen	-	4017361	Blood urea nitrogen measurement	Measurement
	All sites	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
	HSJD	8840	milligram per deciliter	Unit

Glucose	-	3013826	Glucose [Moles/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	-			
	All sites	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
	HSJD	8840	milligram per deciliter	Unit
Direct bilirubin	-	4118986	Bilirubin measurement	Measurement
	HSJD, GOSH, HUS	8749	micromole per liter	Unit
	UC2, Erasmus	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
	HSJD	8840	milligram per deciliter	Unit
Ionized calcium	-	44789220	Ionised calcium measurement	Measurement
	All sites	8753	millimole per liter	Unit

PCT	-	3046279	Procalcitonin [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
	UC2, HSJD	8842	nanogram per milliliter	Unit
	Erasmus	8725	nanogram per liter	Unit
	GOSH, HUS	8748	microgram per liter	Unit
MR-proADM	-	42536081	Adrenal medulla hormone	Observation
	UC2, HSJD	8736	nanomole per liter	Unit
Interleukin-6	-	3033291	Interleukin 6 [Mass/volume] in Body fluid	Measurement
	UC2, HSJD, HUS	8845	picogram per milliliter	Unit

Table 5.25 Arterial blood gas

PHEMS variable of interest	Site using the unit/ SI system	OMOP CDM		
		conceptId	concept name	domain
pH	-	3019977	PH of Arterial blood	Measurement
pCO2	-	3027946	Carbon dioxide [Partial pressure] in Arterial blood	Measurement
	UC2, Erasmus, GOSH, HUS	44777602	kilopascal	Unit
	HSJD	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
PaO2	-	3027801	Oxygen [Partial pressure] in Arterial blood	Measurement
	UC2, Erasmus, GOSH, HUS	44777602	kilopascal	Unit
	HSJD	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit

HCO ₃	-	3008152	Bicarbonate [Moles/volume] in Arterial blood	Measurement
	All sites	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Base excess	-	3003396	Base excess in Arterial blood by calculation	Measurement
	All sites	8753	millimole per liter	Unit

Table 5.26 Venous or capillary blood gas

PHEMS variable of interest	Site using the unit	OMOP CDM		
		conceptId	concept name	domain
pH	-	3012544	pH of Venous blood	Measurement
	-	3009343	pH of Capillary blood	Measurement
pCO ₂	-	3021447	Carbon dioxide [Partial pressure] in Venous blood	Measurement

	-	3023024	Carbon dioxide [Partial pressure] in Capillary blood	Measurement
	UC2, Erasmus, GOSH, HUS	44777602	kilopascal	Unit
	HSJD	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
PaO2	-	3024354	Oxygen [Partial pressure] in Venous blood	Measurement
	-	3028626	Oxygen [Partial pressure] in Capillary blood	Measurement
	UC2, Erasmus, GOSH, HUS	44777602	kilopascal	Unit
	HSJD	8876	millimeter mercury column	Unit
HCO3	-	3027273	Bicarbonate [Moles/volume] in Venous blood	Measurement

	-	3015235	Bicarbonate [Moles/volume] in Capillary blood	Measurement
	All sites	8753	millimole per liter	Unit
Base excess	-	3002032	Base excess in Venous blood by calculation	Measurement
	-	3003129	Base excess in Capillary blood by calculation	Measurement
	UC2, HSJD, Erasmus, GOSH, HUS	8753	millimole per liter	Unit

5.3.3. Mapping assumptions

This section describes each of the mapping assumptions on which the “Report on data requirements and available data mapping” is founded, based on information obtained from each UC lead with regards to UC2:

Firstly, a specific list of drugs representing inotropes and vasopressors has been provided. Given this list without dosages, the RxNorm ingredient level is assumed for drug concept mappings. The same logic should be applied to antibiotic, antifungal, and immunosuppressor drugs.

Secondly, the phrase “present on arrival” in variables refers to presence before (and thereby on) admission to PICU.

Thirdly, the “time point of prediction” in specific variables refers to the beginning of sepsis.

Fourthly, for the gradation of peripheral and central pulse presences, data partners have mixed gradations: “not existing”/“poor”/“vigorous” and “presence”/“absence”. It is assumed both these gradations could be relevant for analysis and the recommendation is thus to map gradations as they exist in the data.

Finally, antibiotic resistance refers to the bacterial sensitivity to the antibiotic.

5.3.4. Variables already in OMOP

Within the UC2 data dictionary, HUS has indicated several OMOP codes for included variables, all of which are captured in Table 5.27. Non-standard concepts are marked in red. For concepts without comments, it is always recommended to select the concept that most accurately reflects the actual event that took place.

Table 5.27 Variables already in OMOP at data sites

PHEMS variable of interest	Suggested by	OMOP CDM		
		conceptId	concept name	domain
Use of urinary catheter	The Hyve	4070667	Urinary catheter	Device
	HUS	4218778	Measurement of systemic arterial pressure	Procedure
	Comment: The concept code suggested by The Hyve specifies the device concept id for the ‘Urinary Catheter’ device. HUS have provided the ‘Insertion of catheter into urinary bladder’ procedure concept. In case the exposure to the device is more important than the insertion			

	<p>itself, it is recommended to use the device concept id accompanied by start- and stop dates. If the insertion of the catheter is more important, use of the procedure concept id with the datetime of the procedure would be recommended.</p> <p>Comment HUS: Yes, seems to be an error. Seems as if arterial blood pressure catheter has gone into wrong row</p> <p>At HUS the angle is always procedure-oriented and mapping to device would not be close to source data.</p>			
Use of arterial blood pressure catheter	The Hyve	45758028	Arterial blood pressure catheter	Device
	HUS	4257824	Measurement of systemic arterial pressure	Procedure
	Comment: The concept code suggested by HUS here is not a standard concept in the latest vocabulary.			
Thromboplastin time	The Hyve	4175016	Partial thromboplastin time, activated	Measurement
		8555	second	Unit
		8523	ratio	Unit
	HUS	3022217	INR in Platelet poor plasma by Coagulation assay	Measurement

	Comment: The concept code suggested by HUS appears to be too specific towards INR, as INR thromboplastin time is recorded as a separate variable. The Hyve suggests the use of the 'Partial thromboplastin time, activated' measurement, as this more accurately reflects the variable as presented in the data dictionary.			
D-dimer	The Hyve	3739360	D-dimer level	Measurement
		8751	milligram per liter	Unit
		8753	millimole per liter	Unit
	HUS	3051714	Fibrin D-dimer FEU [Mass/volume] in Platelet poor plasma	Measurement
Fibrinogen	The Hyve	4094436	Fibrinogen measurement	Measurement
		8636	gram per liter	Unit
		8753	millimole per liter	Unit
		8749	micromole per liter	Unit
	HUS	3016407	Fibrinogen [Mass/volume] in Platelet poor plasma by Coagulation assay Measurement	Measurement

	Comment: Since not all sites use Moles/Volume, per HUS's suggestion, as a unit consistently, it is better to use The Hyve's suggestion as the measurement with the appropriate unit.			
Direct bilirubin	The Hyve	4118986	Bilirubin measurement	Measurement
		8749	micromole per liter	Unit
		8753	millimole per liter	Unit
		8840	milligram per deciliter	Unit
		8749	micromole per liter	Unit
	HUS	3005772	Bilirubin conjugated [Moles/volume] in Serum or Plasma Measurement	Measurement
	Comment: Since not all sites use Moles/Volume, per HUS's suggestion, as a unit consistently, it is better to use The Hyve's suggestion as the measurement with the appropriate unit.			
Ionized calcium	The Hyve	44789220	Ionised calcium measurement	Measurement
		8753	millimole per liter	Unit

	HUS	3016431	Calcium ionized [Moles/volume] adjusted to pH 7.4 in Serum or Plasma	Measurement
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5.3.5. Derived variables

Deriving the length of hospital stay in the analysis stage from mapped admission and discharge dates is good practice, as the dates capture precise information on the beginning and ending of a hospital visit. As such, dates can readily be used to derive length of stay and enable longitudinal analyses better than a “length of stay” record would, making it redundant. Moreover, not creating “length of stay” records reduces the overall load on the database. This same logic is applicable to the “days of event/ procedure/ condition /etc.” variables where start- and stop dates are available.

For the source variable “number of vasopressors or inotropes”, this information can be readily derived by counting the number of drug_exposure records pertaining to vasopressors or inotropes. This again reduces the load on the database and enables more flexible analyses.

Age should not be mapped directly to OMOP but be derived from a birth date.

5.4. Use case 3

5.4.1. Use case 3 description and list of variables

Use case 3 aims to improve the predictive capabilities of a single-center machine learning model that has been constructed to predict and target specific factor levels in hemophilia type A patients during prophylaxis, bleeding or medical procedures requiring optimal hemostasis. This project intends to increase the accuracy of the model by increasing the number of training samples available through the PHEMS federated ecosystem. The variables comprising the dataset in UC3 include demographics, laboratory measurements, coagulation factors, bleeding events and medical procedure specifications (surgical parameters).

5.4.2. Usagi mappings

Below are the suggested mappings tables for UC3 variables of interest. Most mappings are one-to-many, meaning that the variable of interest will be mapped to more than one concept. This can be due to several reasons, such as when mapping to measurements, the mapping will ideally be accompanied by a unit. For example, body weight must be mapped to the body weight concept and the kilogram unit concept. When mapping the blood group measurement, the concept chosen has specific answer or “meas value” concepts associated with the measurement. One can find these [here](#), under the ‘has answer’ tab, listing the various blood group results. If there is no appropriate mapping found, we indicate the conceptId equals 0.

Table 5.28 Patient Characteristics not mapped to the Person table

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
body weight	3025315	body weight	Measurement
	9529	kilogram	Unit
	8504	gram	Unit
height	3036277	body height	Measurement
	8582	centimeter	Unit
	9546	meter	Unit

hemophilia A diagnosis	434007	hereditary factor VIII deficiency disease	Condition
hemophilia A subtype/ severity	4094223	mild hereditary factor VIII deficiency disease	Condition
	4140661	moderate hereditary factor VIII deficiency disease	Condition
	4056830	severe hereditary factor VIII deficiency disease	Condition
blood group	3003694	ABO and Rh group [Type] in Blood	Observation
factor VIII inhibitor status	37393608	factor VIII inhibitor activity	Measurement
	4126681	detected	Measurement
	9190	not detected	Measurement

All variables of interest in the lab measurements are mapped to a measurement concept, with an associated unit concept mapped too. For the measurements of FVIII activity and Von Willebrand factor propeptide, the choice of measurement concept depends on the assay used to measure the substance.

Table 5.29 Lab Measurements

PHEMS variable of interest		OMOP CDM
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		conceptId	concept name	domain
factor VIII inhibitor titer		3024942	coagulation factor VIII inhibitor [Units/volume] in platelet poor plasma by coagulation assay	Measurement
	All sites	44777562	Bethesda units per milliliter	Unit
factor VIII activity measurement		3022520	coagulation factor VIII activated [Units/volume] in platelet poor plasma by coagulation assay	Measurement
		3011832	coagulation factor VIII activity [Units/volume] in platelet poor plasma by Chromogenic assay	Measurement
	Erasmus	8985	International unit per milliliter	Unit
	HSJD, GOSH	9332	international unit per deciliter	Unit
	HUS	8554	percent	Unit
Von Willebrand factor activity measurement		43534000	von Willebrand factor (vWf) activity [Units/volume] in platelet poor plasma by Immunoassay	Measurement

	Erasmus	8985	international units per milliliter	Unit
	HSJD	9332	international units per deciliter	Unit
	HUS	8554	percent	Unit
Von Willebrand factor antigen measurement		3002124	von Willebrand factor (vWf) Ag [Units/volume] in platelet poor plasma by Immunoassay	Measurement
	Erasmus	8985	international units per milliliter	Unit
	HSJD, GOSH	9332	international units per deciliter	Unit
	HUS	8554	percent	Unit
Von Willebrand factor propeptide measurement		3023693	von Willebrand factor (vWf) multimers in platelet poor plasma by Immunoblot	Measurement
		3042349	von Willebrand factor (vWf) cleaving protease inhibitor [Units/volume] in platelet poor plasma	Measurement

	Erasmus	8763	unit per milliliter	Unit
activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT)		4175016	partial thromboplastin time, activated	Measurement
	HSJD, Erasmus	8555	seconds	Unit
	HSJD	8523	ratio	Unit
Prothrombin time (PT)		3034426	prothrombin time (PT)	Measurement
	HUS, Erasmus	8555	seconds	Unit
	HSJD	8523	ratio	Unit
	HSJD	8554	percent	Unit
platelet count		37393863	platelet count	Measurement
		44777588	billion cells per liter	Unit
hematocrit		3009542	Hematocrit [Volume Fraction] of Blood	Measurement

	Erasmus, GOSH	44777604	liter per liter	Unit
	HSJD, HUS	percent	percent	Unit
fibrinogen		3016407	fibrinogen [mass/volume] in platelet poor plasma by coagulation assay	Measurement
		8636	grams per liter	Unit
ALT		3006923	alanine aminotransferase [enzymatic activity/volume] in serum or plasma	Measurement
		8645	units per liter	Unit
AST		3013721	aspartate aminotransferase [enzymatic activity/volume] in serum or plasma	Measurement
		8645	units per liter	Unit

For the treatment variable of interest ‘factor VIII’, the medication given must be mapped to a specific concept depending on the drug, the dose, and the brand recorded. For example, if the medication given was a Kogenate factor VIII injection of 250 U/ml, the concept [Factor VIII 250 UNT Injection \[Kogenate Bayer\]](#) with the code 21154209, should be mapped to the drug_concept_id. Below in Table 5.30, are listed example concepts for FVIII doses of 250 units. For suitable concepts regarding other doses of the medications below, please refer to the following links depending on the brand used. [Advate](#), [Kogenate](#), [Eloctate](#), [Nuwig](#), [Refacto](#), [Novoeight](#). If Emicizumab is also given concomitantly, please use one of the valid concepts listed [here](#). Whether the drug given was given through continuous infusion or a single bolus, will be mapped as another concept, and the answer to that will be mapped to the observation value_as_concept_id field. Desmopressin is mapped in a regular manner with the “desmopressin” RxNorm concept being mapped to the drug_concept_id, and the dose itself mapped to the quantity field.

Table 5.30 Treatments

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
factor VIII	35766745	factor VIII 250 UNT Injection [Advate]	Drug
	21154209	factor VIII 250 UNT Injection [Kogenate Bayer]	Drug
	35831239	factor VIII 250 UNT Injection [Eloctate]	Drug
	40745282	emicizumab 150 MG/ML Injectable Solution [Hemlibra]	Drug
	8985	international unit per milliliter	Unit

factor VIII dose is continuous infusion or bolus dose	40492862	mode of drug administration	Observation
	4129275	continuous infusion	Qualifier
	4265597	by bolus infusions	Qualifier
desmopressin	1517070	desmopressin	Drug
	9655	microgram	Unit
	8576	milligram	Unit
	9662	microgram per kilogram	Unit

In general, when a patient undergoes surgery, the general procedure should be mapped to the Procedure and the Visit table. The first mapping in the table below concerns this process. If one of the procedures or conditions occurs during a medical/ surgical procedure, then it should be mapped in association with the medical/ surgical procedure specifically through the date of the event, and the shared visit ID. For example, if a patient experiences blood loss during the medical/ surgical procedure, the procedure itself should be mapped with the beginning and end dates and the record should be linked to the visit occurrence, through the visit ID. The condition 'intraoperative hemorrhage' should then be mapped to the condition table under the same date details and visit ID. The same logic applies for the procedures and drugs listed below.

Table 5.31 Surgery specific parameters

PHEMS variable of interest	OMOP CDM		
	conceptId	concept name	domain
Medical/ surgical procedure	45888085	medical procedure	Procedure
NaCl administration during surgery	967823	sodium chloride	Drug
	8587	milliliter	Unit
plasma administration during surgery	4028665	plasma transfusion	Procedure
datetime start anesthesia	45888867	anesthesia	Procedure
blood loss during surgery	4308716	intraoperative hemorrhage	Condition
blood transfusion during surgery	37017589	bleeding during medical procedure requiring transfusion	Condition

5.4.3. Variables already in OMOP

In the variable spreadsheet there are some codes suggested from Erasmus for UC3. When possible, a comparison of the suggested codes by the Hyve and the ones available in the spreadsheet are listed below. Mapping suggestions that are in agreement are not listed here.

Table 5.34 Mapping differences

PHEMS variable of interest	Suggested by	OMOP CDM		
		conceptId	concept name	domain
platelet count	Erasmus	3024929	platelets [# /volume] in blood by Automated count	Measurement
	The Hyve	37393863	Platelet count	Measurement
	Comment: Concept suggested by the Hyve is more general			

5.4.4. Derived variables

There are some variables in UC3 that should not be mapped as such in the target model but rather be extracted by querying the OMOP CDM tables. There are two types of derived variables for UC3; information regarding the last known FVIII treatments, and infusion rates. Any relevant information about the 'last known' dose, datetime, or brand should be taken from the last drug_exposure record available. The infusion rate of any factor VIII treatments should be derived from the drug quantity and the total time of the drug administration.

6. Quality assessment of the OMOP CDM

After the data has been converted to the OMOP CDM one should proceed to check the quality of the OMOPed data. All the variable mappings described above are indications of how you can map the variables of interest and in no mean should be taken as an absolute truth. There are multiple OMOP CDM vocabularies that can represent the same event and considering the variability of the source, a detailed assessment of the mapped data is crucial. Within the OHDSI community and the EHDS and DARWIN EU projects, tools have been built to achieve the desired level of confidence regarding the CDM mappings.

6.1. Data Quality Dashboard

We start with the DQD (10). The DQD includes more than 4,000 checks. It is noteworthy that there is no source data information that we can derive from this tool, all the checks involve the converted data. DQD checks span over three categories: conformance, completeness and plausibility. As expected, with such a range of checks there will be a variety of results and interpretations.

Firstly, we start with the tests that are marked failing. There can be different reasons for a failed test. Something needs to be changed in the ETL, for example, a high percentage of unmapped values in the `concept_id` of a table. In this case, check if everything is designed to be mapped properly or if the transformation is executed without issues.

There is a DQD limitation that doesn't apply to your data. For example, there are thresholds embedded in the DQD for measurements as range of values for a hemoglobin measurement. These thresholds have been decided based on expert knowledge and experience; however, they are not always the best metric. If you encounter a failed test in this category, you should join the DQD working group or create a GitHub issue, so the maintenance team is aware and can update the package.

Something needs further investigation. For some DQD checks it is not clear at first glance if there is a source or mapping issue or even if it makes sense for the specific dataset. Examples of failed tests like this can vary. A check might fail because concept id's that are found in the wrong table – a concept with domain observation in the condition occurrence table. Another reason can be that there are gender plausibility issues, namely prostate cancer in females. There may also be an issue with the dates such as the end date occurring before the start date. The list goes on.

Achilles produces a characterization of the OMOPed database (20). Similarly, with the source data, it is advisable to have a general understanding of what information is at hand. A set of plots are generated per clinical event table. For example, you can see general information like the total number of people, the age distribution, or the observation duration as well as plots based on concepts like a specific disease and how it appears on the data.

With the Achilles analysis plots, we can identify inconsistencies, such as “Do we see the correct balance between male and female population?” or “Do we see a change in the codes for a particular drug in the database?” etc.

6.3. CDM Onboarding

One of the many outcomes of the EHDEN project is the CDM Inspection (2,21). This is an R package producing a report combining some general aggregated statistics results with more targeted vocabulary questions and results from a run of the Achilles tool (20,22). For example, custom mappings will be extracted as part of the package output, statistics on the number of mapped and unmapped records as well as the vocabulary tables uploaded in the database, to name a few. There is also information on the technical infrastructure like execution of running queries, versions of all installed R packages, Atlas and WebAPI.

This information is particularly useful to determine data quality issues like “Are the era tables filled correctly?” or to review the vocabulary mappings of the most frequently occurring terms. Also review if the system is running sufficiently and whether some optimizations are required.

6.4. Assessing the use cases

6.4.1. Atlas

When the harmonized data are to be utilized in studies (in the case of PHEMS UCs), certain issues might be revealed as the researchers progress with the study protocol and design. To start, a team of physicians and epidemiologists will create an initial

study protocol, followed by designing the desired patient cohorts in ATLAS. For PHEMS, this is the work WP4 has already put into curating the desired variables. Then, the study team will have to spend their time deciding the correct vocabulary terms to use and translating the protocol phrasing into cohort-specific criteria. This is the aim of this document. The last step is the creation of cohorts for the different UCs.

ATLAS is a tool that helps researchers define and manage patient cohorts using concept sets, supporting the design and execution of observational analyses (11). By creating customized concept sets, researchers can identify patients for research studies based on their specific needs. For WP4 this is highly relevant as a few of the variables of interest will be mapped at different levels of granularity in the data sites. These sets can include various domains such as drugs, conditions, and procedures. While ATLAS is flexible and customizable, it can be challenging to use. An understanding of the OHDSI vocabulary and CDM is essential for using ATLAS's concept sets effectively.

6.4.2. HADES

HADES (Health Analytics Data to Evidence Suit) is a collection of R packages developed by the OHDSI community in order to perform large scale analytics and it includes a number of packages based around Population-level Estimation, Patient-level Prediction, Characterization, Cohort construction and evaluation, and Evidence quality (12,22).

Cohort diagnostics

A great tool from the OHDSI HADES suite to evaluate the cohorts created as well as to get insight into whether the data are fit for the UCs is Cohort Diagnostics (12). Here, it is possible to explore the counts for the cohorts created but also to check if choices in the ETL misplaced patients. For example, an outdated concept has been used for the main disease of interest for the UCs and no patients appear in the target cohort. That is a clear indication that something needs to be discussed and changed, either in the transformation logic or the cohort definition.

Phenotype Library

Phenotype Library is a collection of extensively curated phenotypes by groups of experts across the community (12). It can be a useful insight for commonly researched diseases or drugs and how the OHDSI community sees them.

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8. Appendix

8.1. Questions and answers per site about variables

8.1.1. Questions use case 1

Question: The variable list includes some drug classes rather than individuals. For how these are mapped to the OMOP CDM would be good to know how is this information presented in the source data. For example the *vasoactive drugs*.

- In general the OMOP mapping can be mapped to include an ATC classification code that contains all the individual drugs in the hierarchy.
- Another approach can be the drugs are mapped to the individual codes and at the analysis stage a set of the related concepts is created to capture all the ones of interest.

Answer: All vasoactive drugs related to use case1 are the drugs to calculate the VIS score, i.e.

$$\text{VIS} = \text{dopamine dose } (\mu\text{g/kg/min}) + \text{dobutamine dose } (\mu\text{g/kg/min}) + 100 \times \text{epinephrine dose } (\mu\text{g/kg/min}) + 10 \times \text{milrinone dose } (\mu\text{g/kg/min}) + 10,000 \times \text{vasopressin dose } (\text{U/kg/min}) + 100 \times \text{norepinephrine dose } (\mu\text{g/kg/min})$$

Question: What are the routes for the vasoactive drugs? Are they all intravenous?

Answer: All vasoactive drugs related to use case 1 are intravenous

Question: In variables “Invasive/Non-invasive mechanical ventilation LOS” what does LOS stands for? Length of stay?

Question: For the lab test results, “AST” and “ALT”, we assume that enzyme activity is the only measure of concentration needed. Is this correct?

Answer: The lab tests report the enzyme activity in units/liter.

Question: How is the variable “Age dependent heart rate” appearing in the data? Can this be derived by the dob of the participant and the time of the measurement? Or does it refer to accepted values depending on the age of the patient?

Answer: There is no robust range to be used for normal heart rates in children. This variable is aimed to inform what is observed in the data based on the patients age. The time of the measurement and the dob can be used for this purpose in analysis.

Question: The variable “24hrs holter monitor” is referring to patients with a holter constantly or for patients with holters at a 24 hour interval at the time? And how often are the measurements being monitored and stored in either case?

Answer: The holter monitor can be stored as a procedure and it always lasts 24hours. The outcome of the test is in a text format describing abnormal measurements of the heart rate. There is no need to store the outcome only that the procedure has been performed.

Question: How does a *Pacemaker* differ from an *ICD*. Would it make clinical sense if they are both mapped to a Pacemaker concept?

Answer: The two devices are different two separate concepts to be used Cardiac Pacemaker and Implantable defibrillator.

Question: For the neurological injury variables, the second information, i.e. infraction, seizure and intracranial hemorrhage/ intracranial bleeding, is the injury? Is that assumption correct?

Answer: Yes. The variable refers to an injury leading to the symptom.

Question: The variable “Outpatient specialty” has outcome the number of specialties. Is that number need to be derived at the same visit? Does the source data include all the specific specialty information and will these be mapped?

Answer: Visits to different specialties to be recorded. At the analysis stage the number of these visits are to inform how many organ systems are involved for a patient.

Question: In the variable “*Other specified other operations on ventricles of heart*”, GOSH and Erasmus mention specific operations. What is the intended use of the variable? A list of the available operations in each site? If there are variables outside of the ones specified in the spreadsheet, how can these be distinguished?

Answer: This is a general term to cover unfound operations. The standard concept Other specified other operations on ventricles of heart to be used.

8.1.2. Questions use case 2

Question: The variable list includes some drug classes rather than individuals. For how these are mapped to the OMOP CDM, it would be good to know how is this information presented in the source data. For example the *vasopressors* and *inotropes*.

- In general the OMOP mapping can be mapped to include an ATC classification code that contains all the individual drugs in the hierarchy.

- Another approach can be the drugs are mapped to the individual codes and at the analysis stage a set of the related concepts is created to capture all the ones of interest.

Answer: Inotropes and vasopressors: Epinephrine, Isoproterenol, Dopamine, Dobutamine, Ephedrine, Phenylephrine, Levosimendan, Milrinone, Norepinephrine, Terlipressin, Vasopressin

Question: What is the “*Present on arrival*” referring to in the “*central venous catheter*” variable? Is it intended to capture a more granular information, for example if there was an external/internal transfer, or just the entrance to the PICU?

Answer: “Present on arrival” relates to the presence of the device at admission (that is, if it has already been inserted before the admission to the PICU).

Question: For the “*time point of prediction*” included in multiple variables, which event is defined as the prediction?

Answer: It is the beginning of sepsis.

The variables “*Peripheral pulse*” and “*Central pulse*” include a comment for “*not existing*”/“*poor*”/“*vigorous*”. When looking across the availability that doesn’t seem to appear in the datasets. Also the unit is stated as “*presence*”/“*absence*”. What is the level of information that is of interest for these two variables?

Answer: It would be better if we had the information as “*not existing*”/“*poor*”/“*vigorous*” because it would be more specific. If it is not possible (as it seems from your comments), the “*presence*”/“*absence*” gradation could be enough. The values the different sites have are mixed and therefore mapping to both will be suggested, depending what is available and taking both into account in the analysis stage.

Question: For the “Antibiotic resistance” variable. Does the resistance refer to the infection or the patient?

Answer: It is related to bacterial sensitivity to antibiotics.

- Antibiotics: Penicillin, Ampicillin, Amoxicillin clavulanate, Amoxicillin, Oxacillin, Piperacillin-Tazobactam, Cefazolin, Cefuroxime, Cefotaxime, Cefadroxil, Ceftazidime, Ceftazidime-Avibactam, Cefepime, Ceftolozane-Tazovactam, Ertapenem, Imipenem, Meropenem, Teicoplanin, Vancomycin, Gentamicin, Amikacin, Tobramycin, Erythromycin, Clarithromycin, Azithromycin, Tetracycline, Norfloxacin, Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin, Daptomycin, Clindamycin, Fosfomycin, Nitrofurantoin, Rifampicin, Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole, Linezolid, Mupirocin, Fusidic acid, Colistin
- Antifungal: Fluconazole, Miconazole, Anidulafungin, Voriconazole, Isavuconazole
- Immunopressors:
 - Prednisolone, Methylprednisolone, Hydrocortisone, Dexamethasone
 - Chemotherapy
 - monoclonal antibodies
- Kinds of resistance:
 - ESBL, MRSA
 - Multidrug-resistant, Drug-resistant
 - Erythromycin-resistant, Clindamycin-resistant, Carbapenem-resistant, Vancomycin-resistant, Azole-resistant

8.1.3. Questions use case 3

Question: Are the terms ‘Hemorrhage’ and ‘Bleeding’ to be considered the same medically?

- In UC1 they seem to refer to different concepts
- But in the OMOP vocabularies they are listed as synonyms,
 - e.g. The SNOMED [Hemorrhage](#) concept.

Answer: In the situation of UC3, these synonyms can be used interchangeably. The parameters for bleedings will most likely be dates of the bleeding, not volume of blood for example.

Question: For the FVIII inhibitor titer, are all sites using Bethesda units?

Answer: It is the standard all sites have been talking about during the UC3 meetings. Within the Erasmus MC it is the only used value.

Question: For the Lab Measurement: “ALAT”, only enzyme activity is used, no other form of concentration/level. Is this correct?

Answer: This is correct.

Question: For the Lab Measurement: “ASAT”, only enzyme activity is used, no other form of concentration/level. Is this correct?

Answer: This is correct.

Question: For Treatment: “FVIII concentrate of dose”,

- The example values are “Advate” or “Kogenate”, but these have varying dose/concentrations. Is this correct?

Answer: The main point here is the concentration, where the type of medication should be the brand name (“Advate” or “Kogenate”).

Question: For Lab measurements: “Brand FVIII concentrate around last dose of FVIII activity measurement”: Example values are “Advate” or “Kogenate”, but there is no concentrate information recorded there. Can you specify what information you want recorded, are able to acquire regarding this variable?

- Many subtypes of Advate and Kogenate are standard. They are just more specific and may or may not be applicable depending on what they have. It seems the best applicable concept can only be determined on a case-by-case basis.

Answer: In this instance, it is important to know the blood level and the last given FVIII-concentration brand (from the treatment section). When switching between the two variants, the medication concentrations can spike severely depending on the assay used for determining the blood level. Knowing if the brand was switched with the last dose is important for interpreting the results. So, in this case, if we can use the blood level including the type of FVIII of the last dosage concentration, that would be ideal.

Question: Prophylaxis schedule (e.g. in treatment plan or notes).

- What is the format of this variable?
- Is it consistent for each patient?

Answer: Erasmus is going to make a predictive model for the prophylaxis schedule, since most of the sites do not register these parameters in a standardized way.

Question: For the Patient characteristic: “FVIII genotyping / mutation”, what is the format of the data recorded?

Answer: Due to the unavailability of this parameters in all sites, including our own, we decided to drop this parameter for now.